

COVID-19: A 3-year Review Update of the Neurological Aspects of the 21st Century Pandemic From Etiology to Neuro-psychiatric Implications

Joe F. Bolanos^{1,2}, Kevin Morris^{1,2}, Nataliya Bilger^{1,2}, Love Kumar^{1,2}, Vicky Yamamoto^{1,2}, Babak Kateb^{1,2}

1. Society for Brain Mapping and Therapeutics
2. World Brain Mapping Foundation

Abstract

Coronavirus disease (COVID-19) is a severe infectious disease that has claimed >1 million lives and infected over a hundred million people in the United States in the last three years. The elderly population is most severely affected. New data suggests that people vaccinated have also been infected, but with less severity. Thus, vaccinations help reduce mortality and morbidity.

Established evidence has shown that the virus causes hemorrhagic and immunologic responses that impact all organs, including the lungs, kidneys, and brain, as well as the musculoskeletal system.

This poster aims to provide a comprehensive three-year review update of the SARS-CoV-2-induced neurological diseases, modes of infection, and prolonged complications.

Methods

This is a literature review poster. The goal is to investigate and assess the current literature on repercussions of COVID-19 on the central nervous system. The research design method is a scientific evidence-based rapid review. Standard literature and database searches were implemented, and relevant material was gathered and extracted information evaluated.

Introduction

Human coronaviruses (HCoVs) and other respiratory viruses may enter the central nervous system (CNS) hematogenously or via the ethmoidal cribriform plate by a retrograde neuronal route. There is an infection of the blood-brain barrier's (BBB) endothelial cells and the blood-cerebrospinal fluid barrier's epithelial cells in the choroid plexus brain's ventricles or leukocytes that become hematogenous propagation vectors to the brain.

Virus-induced neuropathology has been proposed to be the dysregulation of the BBB, which is most likely brought on by a confluence of viral and host factors, which can include secreted viral proteins, inflammatory mediators, antiviral therapies, drugs, and aging.

Neurons and glial cells express ACE2 receptors in the CNS. Recent studies suggest that activated glial cells contribute to neuroinflammation and the devastating effects of SARS-CoV-2 infection on the CNS. The critical role of the S and E proteins in HCoVs, and the slow movement of the blood in the brain's microcirculation, might aid in the interaction of the SARS-CoV-2 S-protein (figure 1) with the ACE2 receptor expressed in the capillary endothelium

Fig.1 Illustration of COVID-19 Structure. Illustrated by Dr. Joe Bolanos

Since ACE2 receptors are densely found in the respiratory and digestive tract, nasal epithelium, and tongue, suggesting that the virus may affect the nervous system and significantly impact some senses.

Researchers suggest three different pathways and associated pathological mechanisms of action due to the neuroinvasion of SARS-CoV-2. These are depicted in figure 2

1. A Olfactory pathway via the trigeminal nerve
2. Vagus nervous pathway in connection with the lungs
3. Gut-brain axis pathway a consequence of the effects of a systemic infection

COVID-19 NEUROLOGICAL ENTRANCE AND MAIN MECHANISM OF ACTION

Fig.2 Illustration of COVID-19 Neurological Entrance and main Mechanism of Action. Illustrated by Dr. Nataliya Bilger

Results

Since the first case observed in Wuhan in 2019, COVID-19-infected patients have presented with a wide range of CNS symptoms from mild to severe. The commonly reported symptoms in several publications are described in Table 1.

	CNS =24.8%		PNS = 8.9%	
Dizziness	16.80%	Smell impairment	5.6%	
Headache	13.1%	Taste impairment	5.1%	
Altered Consciousness	7.5%	Nerve pain	2.3%	
Acute cerebrovascular disease	2.8%	Vision impairment	1.4%	
Ataxia	5.0%			Skeletal muscle
Seizures	5.0%			Skeletal muscle injury
				10.7%

Table 1: Neurological Symptoms of COVID-19

Even though most neurological manifestations have been non-focal, some cases of severe and critical COVID-19 have been shown to present with strokes. The etiopathological reasons range from inflammation-induced venous and arterial thromboembolism to hypoxia to diffused intravascular coagulation. Most ischemic strokes in these case series were subcortical or due to distal emboli. Some cases were related to other risk factors like atrial fibrillation, diabetes, or hypertension.

Studies have demonstrated infection of brain glial cells: astroglia, and microglia by the virus, causing the induction of proinflammatory cytokines like interleukin 12 (IL-12), p40, tumor necrosis factor α (TNF- α), IL-6, IL-15, and IL-1 beta. This inflammatory cascade leads to immune-mediated demyelination of neurons. By evading the immune system and stimulating neural and glial cells, viruses can travel from the bloodstream to the brain. Due to the concurrent occurrence of the entire inflammatory process, there is an excess production of reactive oxygen species (ROS), which raises the oxidative state.

Long-lasting hypoxia can lead to intracranial hypertension, which can cause BBB disruption, glial cell activation, oligodendroglial cell injury, demyelination, white matter microhemorrhages, and cell damage. The mitochondria of neural cells undergo anaerobic metabolism when hypoxia is present, which causes an excess of the acid lactic. Intracerebral vasodilation, brain edema, obstruction of cerebral blood flow, hypoxic-ischemic encephalopathy, and headache are all brought on by high acidity and a drop in pH.

HCoVs affect some host proteases like cell surface transmembrane or serine proteases, furin, trypsin, and endosomal cathepsins. Cathepsin D, known for its essential role in degrading altered neuronal proteins like an amyloid precursor, alpha-synuclein, and huntingtin, is changed, leading to the accumulation of these proteins, which are prominent in

neurodegenerative diseases like Alzheimer's disease and Parkinson's.

Studies show that the viral infection produces cytokines that impair neuronal firing, causing depression-like symptoms and affecting the mood by altering the serotonin system.

Conclusions

COVID-19 can present a broad spectrum of manifestations, including demyelination and degeneration leading to neurological sequelae. Therefore, healthcare providers must be well informed to prepare better to deal with future consequences of COVID-19 and its range of complications.

COVID-19 raises a new challenge for neuroscience. The SARS-CoV-2 pandemic has implied a change in our lifestyle but also a revolution for science. There is a need to continue identifying, evaluating, and studying new developing neurological symptoms while focusing on reasons for the changes/reductions in initial symptoms.

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